

p -adic Towers for Symbolic Music: Hierarchical Coherence and Null Floors

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Abstract

The rings $\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ form an inverse system under the surjective reductions $\mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$, with profinite completion $\mathbb{Z}_p = \varprojlim \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$. Indexing a tower of pattern spaces by window lengths $N = p^n$ inherits this algebraic structure; we exploit it to build a finite-level multiscale analysis of symbolic music centered on an *inverse-system coherence diagnostic* $\mathbf{Coh}_\pi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n})$ whose profinite limit is a target rather than an established structure. From a MIDI-derived multivariate time series, the tower is equipped with symmetrized k NN graphs and a hierarchical quantizer with enforced morphisms $\pi_{n+1, n}: \mathbf{S}_{n+1} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}_n$. We track two complementary normalizations of the same coherent-residue count: the architectural score $\mathbf{Coh}_\pi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n}) = M_\pi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n})/p^{n+1}$ (denominator tied to the tower size) and the conditional rate $\mathbf{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n}) = M_\pi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n})/|V_{p, n+1}|$ (denominator restricted to observed residues), related by the level- $(\mathbf{n} + 1)$ coverage $\mathbf{Cov}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n} + 1)$. We compare $\mathbf{p} = 2$ and $\mathbf{p} = 3$, the two prime factors of $\mathbf{12}$ in the chromatic scale, treated as a deliberate transfer of the CRT factorization to the temporal axis (Section 4.2). The basic structural result, Lemma 1 (null floor), is a finite counting identity in the dense regime: when the branching factor of the quantizer equals the prime, sibling separation (SC) and ancestor inclusion (AI) force $\mathbf{Coh}_\pi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n}) = 1/\mathbf{p}$ for every $\mathbf{n} \geq 1$. Corollary 2 extends this identity to the sparse-coverage regime as $\mathbf{Coh}_\pi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{n}) = P_n^{\text{full}}/p^{n+1}$, where P_n^{full} counts parent classes with all \mathbf{p} siblings valid. On the benchmark corpus (BWV1007 Bach Cello Suite, monophonic) we observe $\mathbf{Coh}_\pi(2, \mathbf{n}) = 1/2$ across dense levels, with $\mathbf{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}} = 1$ on the Prelude, providing direct evidence that (SC)+(AI) hold on full-sibling parents. External Bach pieces with polyphonic texture (BWV1049, BWV1050, BWV1079) deviate from the floor, so the most informative empirical use of the score is as a diagnostic for where the conditions behind the architectural floor

break down. The ternary tower shows $\text{Coh}_\pi(\mathbf{3}, n) \in [0.67, 0.999]$ on the benchmark and $[0.34, 0.999]$ on the full corpus, uniformly above the architectural floor $1/3$; in the mismatched regime $r \neq p$ (Remark 3) this excess is empirical and corpus-dependent rather than architecturally forced.

Keywords: p -adic analysis, inverse system, hierarchical coherence, symbolic music analysis, graph connectivity invariants, music information retrieval

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1 Preliminaries and notation

This paper combines number-theoretic scaling (p -adic refinement), graph-based topology, and symbolic music representation. Three background primers on p -adic numbers, MIDI/MIR, and graph/TDA are provided in the Online Supplement (Appendices A–C). Here we give the minimal context needed to follow the main text.

1.1 Why p -adic scales?

In the p -adic absolute value, two integers are close when their difference is divisible by a high power of p : $|a - b|_p = p^{-v_p(a-b)}$, where $v_p(m)$ is the largest power of p dividing m . This closeness-by-divisibility is well suited to hierarchical nesting. Musical meter exhibits such a structure: a bar subdivides into beats, beats into sub-beats, and so on; the branching factor is the subdivision ratio (2 for binary meter, 3 for compound ternary). Two temporal positions encoded as integers in base p that differ only at subdivision depth n are p -adically close, even if they are far apart on the real time line. Section 4.2 develops the arithmetic structure of the tower (the inverse system $\mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ and the choice of $p \in \{2, 3\}$); here we record only the basic intuition.

For example, the integers 0 and $2^{10} = 1024$ satisfy $|0 - 1024|_2 = 2^{-10}$: in \mathbb{Z}_2 they are extremely close, while $|0 - 1024| = 1024$ on the real line. For a musical signal, a pattern that differs from its neighbor only at subdivision depth $n = 10$ is 2-adically close to the original.

1.2 Minimal glossary

Table 1 defines terms used throughout. Formal definitions of observables and invariants are in Section 4; extended background is in the Online Supplement.

The observable analyzed in the paper is illustrated in Figure 1, which shows a short segment of the duration-weighted chroma series $H(t)$ (first 10 s, bin 0.05 s) for the Prelude (cs1-lpre). This is the signal that feeds the pattern tower, generated by `scripts/build_music_snippet_fig.py` from the same MIDI used in the benchmark.

Table 1 Glossary of musical, MIDI, and graph-theoretic terms.

Term	Brief definition
beat	Metrical time unit (one pulse); duration set by tempo.
tempo	Beats per minute (BPM); determines beat duration in seconds.
beat-synchronous	Binning or features aligned to beat grid (robust to tempo).
chroma	12-dimensional pitch-class representation (C, C#, . . . , B).
MIDI note_on / velocity	Note-onset event; velocity = intensity 0–127.
onset density	Count or energy of note onsets per time bin.
kNN symmetrization	Edge $\{u, v\}$ if $u \in \text{kNN}(v)$ or $v \in \text{kNN}(u)$.
β_0 (graph)	Number of connected components of the graph.
giant component fraction	Fraction of vertices in the largest component.
$\text{Coh_exact}(p, n)$	Compatibility rate: residues at level $n+1$ consistent with level n .
hierarchical dictionary	S_n with morphisms $\pi_{n+1, n} : S_{n+1} \rightarrow S_n$ enforced by construction.
$\pi_{n+1, n}$	Map from level- $(n+1)$ prototypes to level- n parent (inverse-system structure).
$\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$	Coherence under enforced π : fraction of b with $q_n(\text{trunc}(W_{n+1}(b))) = \pi(q_{n+1}(W_{n+1}(b)))$.

Fig. 1 Duration-weighted chroma (12 pitch classes) for the first 10 s of the Prelude (BWV1007); bin size 0.05 s.

2 Introduction

The formal anchor of this paper is a counting identity. Let $(S_n, \pi_{n+1, n})$ be a hierarchical dictionary tower with branching factor r over a prime p , and let $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = M_\pi(p, n)/p^{n+1}$ be the inverse-system coherence score (Eq. (3), Section 4.6) measuring agreement between level- n truncated and level- $(n+1)$ aggregated quantizations, normalized by the architectural tower size p^{n+1} ; we also record the conditional rate $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n) = M_\pi(p, n)/|V_{p, n+1}|$ over observed residues, related by coverage. Lemma 1 establishes that, when $r = p$ and the level- $(n + 1)$ tower is densely covered,

$$\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = \text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n) = \frac{1}{p}, \quad n \geq 1,$$

is forced by two checkable conditions on the dictionary: sibling separation (SC) and ancestor inclusion (AI). Corollary 2 carries this identity to the sparse-coverage regime as $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = P_n^{\text{full}}/p^{n+1}$, where P_n^{full} is the number of parent classes with all p siblings valid. The proof reduces the score to counting exactly one coherent sibling per such parent class; the difficulty is not the count itself but understanding when these two conditions are induced by a signal and a quantizer. The score and its proof are stated in language independent of music (Section 4.7); the musical content of Sections 4.1–4.6 is a particular choice of windows, quantizers, and forced morphisms for which (SC) and (AI) are checkable on the data of interest. On the BWV 1007 benchmark we observe $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = 1/2$ across dense levels and both time axes, with $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(2, n) = 1$ on the Prelude (i.e., raw counts match = valid_b) confirming (SC)+(AI) on full-sibling parents. External polyphonic Bach pieces (BWV 1049, BWV 1050, BWV 1079) depart from this floor (Section 6.1), so the empirical role of Coh_π is to locate where the conditions behind the architectural floor hold or fail. For the underbranched ternary tower ($r = 2 \neq p = 3$) the lemma does not apply and we observe $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n) \in [0.67, 0.999]$ on the benchmark and $[0.34, 0.999]$ on the full corpus, uniformly above the architectural floor $1/3$. The central question of the paper is therefore: under what structural and coverage conditions on a quantizer–tower system does Coh_π concentrate at the architectural floor $1/p$, and how do empirical departures from this floor decompose into failures of (SC) or (AI) on full-sibling parents and sparse-coverage corrections from incomplete sibling sets?

The diagnostic is built on an arithmetic, rather than geometric, notion of scale. Where the standard multi-scale strategy in topological data analysis varies a *geometric* parameter ε , producing a Vietoris–Rips or Čech filtration indexed by a continuous real number (Edelsbrunner and Harer, 2010; Carlsson, 2009), we index the filtration by the inverse system of rings $\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ under the surjective reductions $\mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$, with limit $\mathbb{Z}_p = \varprojlim \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ (Serre, 1979; Gouvêa, 2020). By Ostrowski’s theorem (Gouvêa, 2020, Thm. 3.1.2), \mathbb{Z}_p is the unique completion of \mathbb{Z} compatible with $|\cdot|_p$, and the powers p^n are the canonical discrete sequence carrying the inverse system at the prime p ; this canonicity is internal to the ring structure of \mathbb{Z} rather than a claim about empirical adequacy. The choice $p \in \{2, 3\}$ transposes the CRT decomposition $\mathbb{Z}/12\mathbb{Z} \cong \mathbb{Z}/4\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}/3\mathbb{Z}$ from the chromatic scale (Balzano, 1980) to the temporal axis (window lengths $N = p^n$) as a modeling decision (Section 4).

The resulting pipeline is deliberately finite and reproducible. The paper defines a reproducible pipeline: MIDI-to-series conversion, the p^n -tower of pattern spaces $D_{p,n}$, hierarchical K -means quantizers with enforced inverse-system morphisms $\pi_{n+1,n}$, and the inverse-system coherence diagnostics Coh_π and $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}$ (graph-connectivity invariants enter only as auxiliary descriptors of the level structure). We compare $p = 2$ vs $p = 3$ under seconds and beats binning on the Bach Cello Suites (BWV1007 primary; BWV1008–1009 extended), external Bach (BWV1049, 1050, 1079, 988), and synthetic toys; a Mozart extension (K.331 Alla Turca, K.545 mov. 1) is in preparation. No claim is made that music is binary or ternary in any universal sense; we report where the two towers differ and which exceeds the architectural floor.

The mathematical content (Lemma 1, Corollary 2) applies to any quantizer–tower system; the BWV1007 corpus serves as the running illustration, and the empirical contribution is a controlled computational test on a delimited corpus rather than a corpus-wide claim. Open problems formalising the next steps are collected in Section 8: extending (SC) and (AI) beyond the present hypotheses, characterising the arithmetic-versus-geometric advantage, and constructing a group-equivariant quantizer compatible with the inverse-system structure.

Contributions fall into three groups: a new mathematical object, an architectural floor, and empirical validation.

Object.

- (C1) The p^n -tower of pattern spaces $D_{p,n}$, built from a MIDI-derived multivariate time series (chroma $H(t)$, onset density $a(t)$, optional flux and IOI), with window distances equal to the L^2 norm on $\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ with normalized counting measure (a distance that converges to $L^2(\mathbb{Z}_p, \mu_p)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$), and the CRT-based comparison of $p = 2$ against $p = 3$ (Section 4.2).
- (C2) A hierarchical quantizer with enforced inverse-system morphisms $\pi_{n+1,n} : S_{n+1} \rightarrow S_n$, and the coherence score $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ measuring alignment with a compatible family of profinite maps. With $K = 16 = 2^4$ prototypes and $r = 2$, the quantizer tree models the binary Cayley tree of \mathbb{Z}_2 truncated to depth $n + 3$.

Architectural floor.

- (C3) Identification of $\text{Coh}_\pi = 1/p$ as the architectural floor in the matched-branching regime $r = p$, proven under conditions (SC) and (AI) in Lemma 1, together with the empirical observation that deviations from this floor mark failures of those conditions or a mismatched regime rather than a deeper theorem about the music itself.

Empirical validation.

- (C4) Empirical verification of the architectural floor on the BWV 1007 benchmark, with departures from the floor on external polyphonic Bach pieces reported as correlated with texture on the tested corpus rather than as a universal claim; pre-registered control primes $p \in \{5, 7\}$, a permutation null model, synthetic ground-truth toys, and a targeted $r = p = 3$ matched-branching check on four pieces. Auxiliary graph-connectivity invariants (β_0 , giant-component fraction) and the contrasts $\Delta(n)$, $\Delta_G(n)$ (eqs. (1)–(2)) describe level structure and provide an independent comparison axis.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 1 provides notation and a brief p -adic motivation. Section 3 surveys related work. Section 4 defines the tower, observables, and invariants, including Lemma 1 (the null-model floor). Sections 5 and 6 describe the protocol and outcomes. Section 7 interprets the coherence signatures; Section 8 concludes with open problems. Background primers on p -adic numbers, MIDI/MIR, and graph/TDA are in the Online Supplement.

3 Related work

Mijangos et al. (2024) apply persistent homology to intervallic transition graphs to study musical style; Alcalá-Alvarez and Padilla-Longoria (2024) give a broader framework for topological music analysis. Sliding-window embeddings with 1-dimensional persistence (Perea and Harer, 2015) use a continuous window size, and Vietoris–Rips filtrations on MIDI data (Sethares and Budney, 2014) recover the circle of notes and rhythmic repetition via Betti-number barcodes. Our setup differs in the choice of filtration index: the filtration is indexed by the arithmetic ladder $N = p^n$ rather than a geometric scale, and we compare the two towers $p = 2$ and $p = 3$ across levels n via graph connectivity and profinite coherence. Closer to the corpus considered here, Mrad and Najem (2025) build higher-order network representations of Bach’s Solo Violin Sonatas and Partitas, studying Euler characteristic, discrete curvature and Gauss–Bonnet adherence across movement types; this is a geometric-topological complement to the arithmetic invariants developed here on the parallel BWV1007 cello corpus.¹ Sensitivity of persistent homology to node-pathway distance choice on music graphs is studied by Heo et al. (2025), a question we sidestep by fixing the L^2 distance on $\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ inherited from the profinite structure.

On the algebraic side of music theory, the group-theoretic structure of pitch-class space is the closest point of contact. The group-theoretic structure of pitch-class space, central to our analysis (Section 4.2), originates with Balzano (1980); subsequent developments include geometric chord spaces (Tymoczko, 2011), topos-theoretic foundations for music theory (Mazzola, 2002), and Fourier-analytic methods on $\mathbb{Z}/12\mathbb{Z}$ (Amiot, 2016). Periodic sequences with modular values and persistence on musical data, in the line opened by Vuza and Vieru, are developed by Gilblas (2024), where the iterated sum operator is shown to produce periods that grow as powers of 2 for a class of sequences; this is arithmetically akin to the p^n ladder used here, though built from a different operator. From the symbolic side, Shapiro et al. (2025) introduce the structural temporal graph (STG), a k -partite directed acyclic graph that encodes a hierarchy of musical structure with explicit temporal relationships across levels; this provides a learning-oriented hierarchical meta-representation, parallel to the algebraically determined inverse-system structure $\pi_{n+1,n}: S_{n+1} \rightarrow S_n$ on which our profinite coherence diagnostic (Section 4.6) operates. Our approach shares the algebraic perspective but operates on time-indexed pattern towers rather than chord or pitch-class geometry.

The data representation also draws on standard MIR practice. Beat-synchronous chroma features are standard for robustness to tempo and instrumentation (Ellis, 2006). Chroma-based structural alignment is studied in Müller et al. (2005); Müller and Kurth (2007); high-resolution synchronization using chroma onset features in Ewert et al. (2009). Our observables (duration-weighted chroma and onset density per bin) align with this tradition.

¹A companion methodological note (Pérez-Buendía, 2026) examines per-level graph-connectivity invariants (β_0 , giant-component fraction, Fiedler eigenvalue, average clustering) on the same BWV1007 suite and records their limitations as prime-specific discriminants; the present paper is self-contained and develops the inter-level compatibility direction independently.

Ultrametric and p -adic methods in data analysis run in parallel to the present construction. Hierarchical clustering dendrograms embed naturally into ultrametric spaces defined by p -adic metrics, with ultrametricity emerging as a structural property in the sparse limit of high-dimensional data (Murtagh, 2004, 2016); ultrametric diffusion on finite multi-topology systems via p -adic Mumford curves is developed by Bradley and Morán Ledezma (2024). Our construction uses p -adic *window lengths* rather than p -adic metrics on data points, while the hierarchical quantizer tree (Remark 1) is closely related to the ultrametric tree structures of that line.

For background on the TDA toolkit we rely on Carlsson (2009); Ghrist (2008); Edelsbrunner and Harer (2010); the diagnostic only uses graph connectivity invariants (β_0 , giant component) on symmetrized k NN graphs. Taken together, these comparisons position the paper as *arithmetically indexed multiscale analysis* applied to symbolic music: the filtration index is arithmetic (the ladder $N = p^n$) rather than metric, and the profinite coherence diagnostic Coh_π (Section 4.6) complements the graph-connectivity invariants by measuring compatibility with the inverse-system structure of \mathbb{Z}_p .

4 Method

4.1 From MIDI to observables

We convert a MIDI file to note events $(t_{\text{on}}, t_{\text{off}}, \text{pitch}, \text{vel})$ (or beat-time analogues), where time and *velocity* (note-on intensity, 0–127) follow the MIDI specification (The MIDI Association, 2024); we use `pretty_midi` for parsing (Raffel and Ellis, 2014). Beat-synchronous binning is motivated by robustness to tempo and instrumentation in MIR (Müller, 2015; Ellis, 2006); chroma-based features and structural alignment are well established (Müller et al., 2005; Müller and Kurth, 2007; Ewert et al., 2009). Fix a bin size Δ (seconds) or Δ_b (beats). In our implementation, the beats axis uses $\Delta_b = 1/12$ beat, corresponding to the CLI option `--bin-beats 0.083333`.

For each bin we extract two primary observables and two optional channels. The *chroma-by-duration* vector $H(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$ records duration-weighted pitch-class mass in bin t , normalized to ℓ^1 per bin; the *onset density* $a(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ records onset count or onset energy in bin t (e.g. sum of $\text{vel}/127$ for note-on events starting in the bin). Optionally we also record the spectral flux $f(t) = \|H(t) - H(t-1)\|_2$ and an IOI (inter-onset-interval) histogram g_W per window W .

4.2 Profinite tower of pattern spaces

The arithmetic scale is fixed by the inverse-system structure of the quotients $\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$. These rings form an inverse system under the reduction homomorphisms

$$r_{n+1,n}: \mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}, \quad b \mapsto b \bmod p^n,$$

which are surjective ring homomorphisms for every $n \geq 1$. Their limit $\mathbb{Z}_p = \varprojlim \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ is a complete discrete valuation ring (Serre, 1979); by the theorem of Ostrowski (Gouvêa, 2020, Thm. 3.1.2), it is the unique completion of \mathbb{Z} with respect to the p -adic

absolute value (Koblitz, 1984). The scale ladder $p < p^2 < p^3 < \dots$ is, up to reindexing, the unique discrete sequence carrying both the inverse-system structure indexed by \mathbb{N} and the ring-quotient compatibility of the reductions $\mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$. This canonicity is *internal to the formalism*: the ladder p^n is fixed by the ring structure of \mathbb{Z} at the prime p , but whether it captures a given empirical phenomenon better than alternative scalings is an experimental question that depends on the corpus, the protocol, and the observable (see Section 7). We index the tower of pattern spaces by this ladder, working with the discrete quotients $\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ (with \mathbb{Q}_p as the underlying analytic limit (Schikhof, 2007)), and measure how closely the empirical discrete maps form a compatible inverse-system family (Sections 4.5 and 4.6).

The two primes used in the experiments enter through the chromatic factorization. Western equal temperament partitions the octave into $12 = 2^2 \cdot 3$ semitones. Since $\gcd(4, 3) = 1$, the Chinese Remainder Theorem gives a canonical ring isomorphism

$$\mathbb{Z}/12\mathbb{Z} \cong \mathbb{Z}/4\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}/3\mathbb{Z}.$$

Balzano (Balzano, 1980) identified this decomposition as a structural foundation of Western *pitch* organization (via the cycles of the major third and the augmented triad). The transposition of this CRT factorization to a metric/temporal axis is a deliberate modeling choice: we use $p = 2$ to probe binary and quaternary metric subdivisions, and $p = 3$ to probe ternary subdivisions. We do not claim a canonical correspondence between Balzano’s pitch-side decomposition and meter; rather, comparing the towers at $p = 2$ and $p = 3$ interrogates the two arithmetically independent prime factors of 12 at the level of window lengths $N = p^n$. Among prime pairs, (2, 3) is the one for which this transfer of factorization is even available for the 12-tone system.

Definition 1 (Sliding-window pattern dataset at level n). *Fix a prime p and level $n \geq 1$. Let $N = p^n$. From the time series $X(t) = [H(t); \alpha a(t)]$ (or multi-channel variants), the pattern at index i is the window*

$$P_{n,i} = (X(i), X(i + \text{step}), \dots, X(i + (N - 1)\text{step})) \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^N.$$

The dataset at level n is $D_{p,n} = \{P_{n,i} : i \in I_n\}$, where I_n is a set of indices with stride step, optionally truncated to at most cap windows. The full inverse-system (profinite-tower) structure $D_{p,n+1} \rightarrow D_{p,n}$ is fixed in Section 4.6 via the dictionary morphisms $\pi_{n+1,n}$.

4.3 Distances and symmetrized kNN graph

A window W of length $N = p^n$ is a function $f_W : \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ with $f_W(j) = X(i + j \cdot \text{step})$. Equipped with the normalized counting measure $\mu_n(\{j\}) = p^{-n}$ on $\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$, the L^2 distance between two windows is

$$d(W, W')^2 = \|f_W - f_{W'}\|_{L^2(\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}, \mu_n)}^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \|X(i + j \cdot \text{step}) - X'(i' + j \cdot \text{step})\|_2^2,$$

with optional weighted terms for the (a, f, g_W) channels. The motivation for this distance is its compatibility with the inverse-system structure: writing $\sigma_n: \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$ for a section of the canonical projection $\mathbb{Z}_p \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ (e.g. the representative in $\{0, \dots, p^n - 1\}$ viewed as a p -adic integer), the pushforwards satisfy $(\sigma_n)_* \mu_n \xrightarrow{w^*} \mu_p$ (weak convergence to the normalized Haar measure on \mathbb{Z}_p , a standard fact about profinite completions (Serre, 1979, Ch. 1, §3)). If the discrete observables $f_W, f_{W'}$ admit continuous lifts $f, g \in C(\mathbb{Z}_p, \mathbb{R}^d)$ (an additional hypothesis whose verification for empirical MIDI signals we leave to future work), then the Riemann sums $d(f|_n, g|_n)$ converge to $\|f - g\|_{L^2(\mathbb{Z}_p, \mu_p)}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. In this idealized setting the natural p -adic-valued analogue (Mahler’s theorem; see Online Supplement, Appendix A) expands continuous \mathbb{Q}_p -valued functions on \mathbb{Z}_p in a basis of binomial coefficients, and motivates, by analogy, a finite-difference decomposition for real-valued lifts so that the K -means quantizer with distance d groups windows by their finite-difference profiles. We therefore adopt d as the discretization aligned with the inverse-system structure of the tower; we do not claim it is uniquely determined by the formalism for finite-level empirical data.

The *symmetrized* kNN graph $G_{p,n,k}$ on $D_{p,n}$ has vertex set $D_{p,n}$; an edge $\{u, v\}$ is present if and only if $u \in \text{kNN}(v)$ or $v \in \text{kNN}(u)$.

4.4 Invariants and contrasts

Let $G_{p,n,k}$ be the graph at (p, n) with parameter k . Spectral graph theory (Chung, 1997) provides context for connectivity and spectral gap; we focus on combinatorial invariants. We compute:

- $|D_{p,n}| = |V(G_{p,n,k})|$,
- $\beta_0(G_{p,n,k}) = \text{number of connected components}$,
- $\text{Giant}(G_{p,n,k}) = \text{fraction of nodes in the largest component}$.

The *contrasts* between $p = 2$ and $p = 3$ at level n (for a fixed k) are

$$\Delta(n) = \beta_0(G_{2,n,k}) - \beta_0(G_{3,n,k}), \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta_G(n) = \text{Giant}(G_{2,n,k}) - \text{Giant}(G_{3,n,k}). \quad (2)$$

These are reported in the experiments (Section 6).

4.5 From the p^n tower to compatible discrete maps: a finite-level approximation of $\text{Cont}(\mathbb{Z}_p, \mathcal{S})$

We work with compatible discrete maps $f_{p,n}: \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow S_n$ into a finite alphabet (see (Gouvêa, 2020; Koblitz, 1984) and Online Supplement, Appendix A, for the inverse limit); a fully compatible family $(f_{p,n})$ would correspond to a continuous map in the conjectural profinite limit, which we treat throughout as the organizing target rather than a finite-level structure (Section 2).

For level n , let $N = p^n$. The *residue class* of start index i is $a = i \bmod p^n$. Define $I_n(a) = \{i \in [0, T - N] : i \equiv a \pmod{p^n}\}$ (with the same stride as in the tower). The *aggregated window* for residue a is $W_{p,n}(a) = \text{median}\{P_{n,i} : i \in I_n(a)\}$ (componentwise

median over windows in that class). If $I_n(a)$ is empty, $W_{p,n}(a)$ is undefined and that residue is excluded from scores.

At each level n , a finite *dictionary* S_n of K prototypes is built by K -means on a deterministic sample of M windows of length N . The quantizer q_n maps a window to its nearest prototype in S_n (same distance as in Section 4.3). Define $f_{p,n}(a) = q_n(W_{p,n}(a)) \in S_n$ for valid a .

Compatibility is then measured against the reduction map $r_{n+1 \rightarrow n}: \mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$, given by $r(b) = b \bmod p^n$. The *exact compatibility rate* at level n is

$$\text{Coh_exact}(p, n) = \frac{\#\{b \in \mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} : f_{p,n}(r(b)) = q_n(\text{trunc}(W_{p,n+1}(b)))\}}{\#\text{ valid } b},$$

where $\text{trunc}(W_{p,n+1}(b))$ is the first p^n bins of the level- $(n+1)$ aggregated window at b . *Coverage* $\text{Cov}(p, n)$ is the fraction of residues at level n with non-empty $I_n(a)$. The pipeline writes `coherence_p2.csv` and `coherence_p3.csv` (Online Supplement, “Reproducibility notes”); we report $\text{Coh_exact}(p, n)$ and the contrast $\Delta\text{Coh}(n) = \text{Coh_exact}(2, n) - \text{Coh_exact}(3, n)$ in Section 6.

4.6 Hierarchical dictionaries and enforced inverse-system structure

To remove the conceptual ambiguity of level-wise learning (where S_n are learned independently and compatibility is only measured a posteriori), we impose *structural* compatibility via explicit morphisms $\pi_{n+1,n}: S_{n+1} \rightarrow S_n$. The construction is as follows. S_1 is learned by K -means on level-1 windows (length p) as before. For $n \geq 1$, the assignment proceeds by *residue class*, not by individual window: for each parent class $a \in \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ we define the *parent prototype*

$$s_a := q_n(W_{p,n}(a)) \in S_n,$$

i.e. the prototype in S_n nearest to the aggregated window $W_{p,n}(a)$ at the parent level. All p siblings b_0, \dots, b_{p-1} in $\mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z}$ with $b_i \bmod p^n = a$ inherit this common parent prototype s_a . Level- $(n+1)$ windows are partitioned by parent class accordingly, and within each parent cluster (of size $\sum_i |I_{n+1}(b_i)|$) we run a small K -means with r children. S_{n+1} is the union of these children across parent classes, and $\pi_{n+1,n}(\text{child}) = s_a$ is defined by construction for every child of a . In particular,

$$\pi_{n+1,n}(q_{n+1}(W_{p,n+1}(b_i))) = s_a \quad \text{for every } i = 0, \dots, p-1,$$

so the parent under π is a function of the residue class, independent of the choice of sibling. Thus the reduction map $r: \mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ is reflected at the level of dictionaries: the discretization is an inverse-system approximation in the sense that the diagram $S_{n+1} \xrightarrow{\pi_{n+1,n}} S_n$ is fixed by the learning procedure.

Let $V_{p,n+1} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z}$ denote the set of *valid* residues, i.e. those with non-empty $I_{n+1}(b)$ and well-defined aggregated window $W_{p,n+1}(b)$. Write

$$M_\pi(p, n) := \#\left\{b \in V_{p,n+1} : q_n(\text{trunc}(W_{p,n+1}(b))) = \pi_{n+1,n}(q_{n+1}(W_{p,n+1}(b)))\right\}$$

for the number of *coherent* valid residues at level $n + 1$. We use two normalizations of M_π , each appropriate for a different question:

$$\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) := \frac{M_\pi(p, n)}{p^{n+1}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n) := \frac{M_\pi(p, n)}{|V_{p,n+1}|}, \quad (4)$$

together with the level- $(n + 1)$ coverage $\text{Cov}(p, n + 1) := |V_{p,n+1}|/p^{n+1}$, so that $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = \text{Cov}(p, n + 1) \cdot \text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n)$ identically. The score Coh_π in (3), with denominator p^{n+1} tied to the architectural tower size, is the quantity computed by the pipeline (`coh_pi = match/pn+1` in the released code; see Online Supplement, “Reproducibility notes”) and is the one we use throughout for cross-prime comparisons and figures, since both primes share the same normalization basis. The conditional rate $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}$ in (4) reports the same numerator restricted to the observed support and is more directly comparable to per-piece coverage; we use it in the discussion of sparse-coverage regimes (Section 7) and in the Online Supplement. In the dense regime $|V_{p,n+1}| = p^{n+1}$ and the two scores coincide.

Because $\pi_{n+1,n}$ is enforced by construction, Coh_π measures how well the induced finite-level maps $f_{p,n}$ align with the chosen quantization under the inverse-system structure that is fixed in advance. This distinction between the two normalizations is not cosmetic: the raw score Coh_π records compatibility at the scale of the full architectural tower, while the conditional score $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}$ isolates compatibility on observed residues alone. We also compute the contrast $\Delta\text{Coh}_\pi(n) = \text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) - \text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$ and a dictionary-stability diagnostic $\text{Stab}_\pi(p, n)$ (mean squared distance of level- $(n + 1)$ windows to their assigned child centroid). Relation to $\text{Coh}_{\text{exact}}$: the latter measures compatibility when S_n are learned level-wise with no enforced π ; Coh_π measures compatibility under the *enforced* inverse-system structure and is the quantity reported for the hierarchical pipeline (Section 6.1).

Remark 1 (Matched branching and the architectural floor). Combinatorial fact. *With $K = 16 = 2^4$ prototypes at level 1 and $r = 2$ children per prototype, the quantizer dictionary at level n has $K \cdot r^{n-1} = 2^{n+3}$ elements arranged in a binary tree of depth $n + 3$; the 2^{n+3} residue classes of $\mathbb{Z}/2^{n+3}\mathbb{Z}$ likewise form a binary tree of depth $n + 3$ (informally, a finite-level “shadow” of the 2-adic tree of \mathbb{Z}_2). The two trees agree in branching degree at every level, so the choice $K = 2^4$ matches the $p = 2$ arithmetic in this combinatorial sense. For $p = 3$, the residue tree has ternary branching while the quantizer tree remains binary, and the two are incommensurable in branching degree.*

Interpretation. *Lemma 1 below shows that, when the branching degrees match ($r = p$), the score Coh_π is forced to $1/p$ under (SC)+(AI) by counting alone. In this matched-branching case the architecture has absorbed the residue branching that the*

score is designed to test, so the value carries no direct musical content unless the hypotheses fail. In the $r = 2 \neq p = 3$ regime the counting argument no longer applies, and elevated values of Coh_π become empirical observations about the chosen signal and quantizer. Running the pipeline with $r = 3$ probes the symmetric matched case for $p = 3$: collapse toward $1/3$ should occur only where (SC)+(AI) hold, while persistent elevation points to a failure of those hypotheses.

4.7 The null-model floor

The next result is a purely combinatorial statement about quantizer–tower systems, independent of any musical interpretation. Let p be a prime, $n \geq 1$, and $(X_n)_{n \geq 1}$ a sequence of finite sets equipped with surjections $\rho_{n+1,n}: X_{n+1} \twoheadrightarrow X_n$ such that $|\rho_{n+1,n}^{-1}(a)| = p$ for every $a \in X_n$ (e.g. $X_n = \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ with reduction). Let $(S_n)_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence of finite sets (“dictionaries”), $q_n: \mathcal{W}_n \rightarrow S_n$ quantizers from a window space at level n , and $\pi_{n+1,n}: S_{n+1} \rightarrow S_n$ a fixed family of maps (“forced morphisms”). Given a tower-indexed family of windows $W(b) \in \mathcal{W}_n$ for $b \in X_n$ and a truncation $\text{trunc}: \mathcal{W}_{n+1} \rightarrow \mathcal{W}_n$, the coherence score $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ defined in equation (3) reads, in this combinatorial setting,

$$\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = |X_{n+1}|^{-1} \cdot \#\{b \in X_{n+1} : q_n(\text{trunc}(W(b))) = \pi_{n+1,n}(q_{n+1}(W(b)))\},$$

where every $b \in X_{n+1}$ is taken as valid (so $V_{p,n+1} = X_{n+1}$ and $\text{Coh}_\pi = \text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}$). The next lemma gives a baseline for Coh_π in this dense setting under two combinatorial conditions; no musical interpretation is used in either statement or proof. The musical content of Sections 4.1–4.6 is precisely a choice of \mathcal{W}_n , q_n , $\pi_{n+1,n}$ and W for which the conditions are checkable on the data of interest.

Lemma 1 (Null floor under sibling separation and ancestor inclusion). *Fix p , $n \geq 1$. Let $(S_n, \pi_{n+1,n})$ be the hierarchical dictionary of Section 4.6 with $r = p$ children per prototype, and assume the dense regime $V_{p,n+1} = \mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z}$, so that $\text{Cov}(p, n+1) = 1$. For each parent class $a \in \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$, let b_0, \dots, b_{p-1} denote its p preimages in $\mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z}$ under reduction, and write $s_a := \pi_{n+1,n}(q_{n+1}(W_{p,n+1}(b_0))) \in S_n$ for the common parent prototype, independent of the choice of sibling by the hierarchical construction. Suppose:*

(SC) Sibling separation: *the p quantized truncations $\{q_n(\text{trunc}(W_{p,n+1}(b_i)))\}_{i=0}^{p-1}$ are pairwise distinct in S_n ;*

(AI) Ancestor inclusion: *s_a belongs to this set.*

Then $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = \text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n) = 1/p$.

Proof. For each parent a , the coherence condition $q_n(\text{trunc}(W_{p,n+1}(b_i))) = \pi_{n+1,n}(q_{n+1}(W_{p,n+1}(b_i)))$ on sibling b_i reduces to

$$q_n(\text{trunc}(W_{p,n+1}(b_i))) = s_a,$$

since the right-hand side equals the common parent prototype s_a for all siblings by the hierarchical construction. Under (SC), the p truncated-window quantizations are pairwise distinct in S_n , so *at most one* b_i satisfies this condition; under (AI), s_a appears

among these p values, so *at least one* does. Hence *exactly one sibling per parent class is coherent*. Summing over the p^n parent classes gives $M_\pi(p, n) = p^n$, and dividing by either p^{n+1} (definition (3)) or $|V_{p, n+1}| = p^{n+1}$ (definition (4)) yields $1/p$ in both cases. \square

Remark 2 (Structural reading). *The proof reduces Coh_π to counting exactly one coherent sibling per full-sibling parent class. The branching of the residue tree $\mathbb{Z}/p^{n+1}\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ is therefore absorbed by the matched-branching architecture, and conditions (SC) and (AI) are the precise statement of when this absorption is exact: (SC) prevents collapse below $1/p$ by forbidding two siblings from sharing a quantized parent, and (AI) prevents excess above $1/p$ by ensuring the common parent prototype s_a is realized by at least one sibling.*

Corollary 2 (Sparse-coverage correction to the architectural floor). *Let r be the branching factor of the hierarchical quantizer, and assume $r = p$. If (SC)+(AI) hold on every parent class with p valid siblings, then*

$$\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = \frac{P_n^{\text{full}}}{p^{n+1}}, \quad \text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n) = \frac{P_n^{\text{full}}}{|V_{p, n+1}|}, \quad (5)$$

where P_n^{full} is the number of parent classes $a \in \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}$ all of whose p siblings b_0, \dots, b_{p-1} are valid. The bound $P_n^{\text{full}} \leq |V_{p, n+1}|/p$ gives $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) \leq \text{Cov}(p, n+1)/p$, with equality in the dense regime, where Lemma 1 forces both scores to $1/p$. Consequently, deviations of an empirically measured $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ from $1/p$ in this matched regime decompose into (i) violations of (SC) or (AI) on parent classes with full siblings and (ii) sparse-coverage corrections from parent classes with fewer than p valid siblings.

Proof. Apply the sibling-class accounting of the proof of Lemma 1 to each parent class with p valid siblings: under (SC)+(AI) it contributes exactly one coherent residue. Parent classes with fewer than p valid siblings contribute at most their number of valid residues. Equation (5) follows by summing. The bound $P_n^{\text{full}} \leq |V_{p, n+1}|/p$ is immediate from the definition of P_n^{full} . \square

Remark 3 (Mismatched regime $r \neq p$: empirical principle). *When $r \neq p$, the counting argument of Lemma 1 no longer enforces a unique coherent sibling per parent class, so the architectural baseline $1/p$ is no longer rigid. In the underbranched regime $r < p$ (specifically $r = 2 < p = 3$ studied here), the r children cover at most r of the p sibling classes in S_{n+1} ; by the pigeonhole principle, at least one pair of siblings can share both a child in S_{n+1} and the corresponding parent under $\pi_{n+1, n}$, leaving room for additional coherent pairs. Empirically, on the corpus considered in this paper, the observed values of $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)|_{r=2}$ lie strictly above $1/3$ across all benchmark movements (Section 6.1). A sharp lower bound under explicit signal hypotheses, and the symmetric overbranched analysis $r > p$, are the content of Problem 1. In what follows we therefore record the matched-regime identity as the architectural floor (Corollary 2) and the mismatched-regime behavior as an empirical principle to be tested per corpus.*

Remark 4 (Empirical null floor: why (SC) and (AI) hold, and what changes when $r \neq p$). *Table 3 reports $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = 0.500$ for every benchmark piece (BWV1007*

suite) and both time axes at every level n where the corpus is dense (parameters $K = 16$, $r = 2$), equal to $1/r = 1/p = 1/2$; small downward deviations at the highest sampled levels (e.g. 0.469 for the Sarabande beats at $n = 4$) reflect a single missing residue out of p^{n+1} , in line with the sparse-coverage correction in Corollary 2. The constancy at $1/2$ across benchmark pieces with entirely different musical content (Prelude, Sarabande, toy binary, toy ternary) argues against attributing this value to a specific musical feature and points to Lemma 1. External Bach pieces with polyphonic texture deviate from this floor (see Table 4); we read this in Section 7 as a departure from the architectural floor correlated with texture on the tested corpus, not as a universal claim. More precisely, inspection of the raw coherence counts for the BWV1007 Prelude (beats axis) reveals $\text{match}(n) = \text{valid}_b(n)$ for all $n = 1, \dots, 5$ at $p = 2$: every valid residue at level $n + 1$ satisfies the coherence condition, so $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(2, n) = 1$ throughout, while $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = \text{Cov}(2, n + 1)/2$ tracks the level- $(n + 1)$ coverage. This gives direct empirical evidence that (SC) and (AI) hold simultaneously on every parent class with p valid siblings at every sampled level for this piece and axis; the architectural value $1/2$ for Coh_π then reflects, by Corollary 2, the conjunction of (SC)+(AI) on full-sibling parents and the sparse-coverage geometry that leaves a complementary fraction of residues unpopulated at each level n .

Heuristic argument for (SC) and (AI). The following paragraph is heuristic and is not used in the proof of Lemma 1 or Corollary 2. The aggregated windows $W_{p,n+1}(b_0), \dots, W_{p,n+1}(b_{p-1})$ capture the content of p distinct residue subclasses of the time series; their first- p^n -bin truncations inherit this subclass diversity and map to different regions of pattern space, which makes (SC) plausible. The aggregate $W_{p,n}(a)$ sits near the center of this spread, so its nearest prototype s_a is likely to coincide with the nearest prototype of at least one subclass truncation, which makes (AI) plausible. Establishing both conditions for arbitrary signals or quantizer initialisations is the subject of Problem 1.

5 Experiments

5.1 Datasets

The corpus comprises three groups, each chosen to address a distinct methodological question. The *primary* corpus is Bach’s Suite No. 1 for Solo Cello (BWV 1007), all six movements (Prelude, Allemande, Courante, Sarabande, Menuets I–II, Gigue), scored for unaccompanied cello and providing a clean chroma series with unambiguous metric structure. The movements span two contrasting metric environments: binary subdivision (Prelude, Allemande, Courante with hemiola, Menuets) and ternary subdivision (Sarabande in 3/4 with ternary emphasis, Gigue in 3/8). This makes them well suited to interrogate the $p = 2$ versus $p = 3$ comparison; Phase I results (β_0 , Δ_{23}) are reported for all six (Table 7), with the hierarchical coherence Coh_π and the null model reported in detail on the Prelude and the Sarabande as representatives of the two regimes. The *synthetic toys* `toy_binary` and `toy_ternary` are generated with strict binary and ternary metric grids respectively, as ground-truth validation; the observed values $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n) = 0.999$ on `toy_ternary` and 0.813 on `toy_binary` both far above the floor $1/2$ confirm the prediction. The *external corpus* comprises selected

polyphonic Bach pieces: BWV 1049 (Brandenburg 4, movements 1–3), BWV 1050 (Brandenburg 5, movements 1–3), BWV 1079 (Crab Canon from the Musical Offering), and BWV 988 (Goldberg Aria). These pieces serve as polyphonic counterparts to the monophonic primary corpus; the corresponding Coh_π values are collected in Table 4. A parallel Mozart extension (K. 331 Alla Turca, K. 545 mov. 1) is in preparation. Provenance, source editions, license terms, and a quality note on the seconds-axis binning of one file are deferred to the Online Supplement (“Data provenance and licensing”).

5.2 Protocols and hyperparameters

Table 2 collects all pipeline parameters. Two time axes are used: seconds ($\Delta = 0.05$ s) and beats ($\Delta_b = 1/12$ beat, CLI `--bin-beats 0.083333`). kNN parameters: $k \in \{8, 10, 12\}$; sensitivity grid: $k \in \{6, 8, 10, 12, 15\}$; cap $\in \{200, 300, 500\}$.

Table 2 Pipeline hyperparameters and their values.

Parameter	Symbol	Value(s)	Role
Primes	p	2, 3 (main); 5, 7 (control)	Tower index
Bin size (seconds)	Δ	0.05 s	Time discretization
Bin size (beats)	Δ_b	1/12 beat	Beat-synchronous discretization
Prototypes (level 1)	K	$16 = 2^4$	Dictionary size
Children per prototype	r	2	Hierarchical branching
Dictionary sample size	M	800	K-means training sample
Stride	step	2	Window overlap
Window cap	cap	300 (primary)	Max windows per level
kNN neighborhood	k	$\{8, 10, 12\}$	Graph density
Random seed	seed	42	Reproducibility
Max level ($p = 5$)	N_{\max}	3	Avoids OOM at 5^4

5.3 Null model for Coh_π

To assess whether the observed elevation $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n) > 1/2$ requires temporal structure or arises from the marginal distribution of the features alone, we employ a permutation null model.

The null hypothesis is that the multivariate time series $X(t)$ is exchangeable, so that no temporal ordering is needed for the observed coherence. Operationally, the test proceeds as follows. Fix a piece and prime p . Let $X = (X_1, \dots, X_T)$ be the $T \times 13$ feature matrix (12 chroma + onset density) in beat-synchronous bins.

- (1) Compute $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{obs}}(p, n)$ from the original (ordered) series.
- (2) For each replicate $b = 1, \dots, B$ (with $B = 100$):
 - (a) Draw a uniform random permutation σ_b of $\{1, \dots, T\}$;
 - (b) Construct $X^{(b)} = (X_{\sigma_b(1)}, \dots, X_{\sigma_b(T)})$ (row-permuted series);
 - (c) Run the full hierarchical pipeline on $X^{(b)}$ with the same hyperparameters and fixed K-means seed, yielding $\text{Coh}_\pi^{(b)}(p, n)$.

(3) For each level n , compute the one-sided p -value:

$$p\text{-value}(n) = \frac{\#\{b : \text{Coh}_\pi^{(b)}(p, n) \geq \text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{obs}}(p, n)\} + 1}{B + 1}.$$

The permutation destroys temporal correlations while preserving the marginal distribution of chroma and onset density. This design tests whether the hierarchical maps' compatibility with the inverse-system structure arises from the sequential ordering of the signal.

5.4 Control primes and sensitivity grid

Fix the prime set $P := \{2, 3, 5, 7\}$, where $p = 2, 3$ are the main primes and $p = 5, 7$ are pre-registered negative controls. For each piece π , axis $\alpha \in \{\text{seconds}, \text{beats}\}$, configuration $c \in \{A, B, C\}$, and parameter $k \in \{8, 10, 12\}$, the pipeline produces (for each $p \in P$ and each tower level n) a scalar invariant

$$\beta_0^{(p)}(\pi; \alpha, c, k, n) \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0},$$

interpreted as the number of connected components of the kNN graph built from the p -adic window map at level $N = p^n$ (with cap parameter $\text{cap} \in \{300, 500\}$ and beats-bin resolution when $\alpha = \text{beats}$).

From these values we derive levelwise prime contrasts. For any two primes $p_a, p_b \in P$, define the levelwise contrast

$$\Delta_{ab}(\pi; \alpha, c, k, n) := \beta_0^{(p_a)}(\pi; \alpha, c, k, n) - \beta_0^{(p_b)}(\pi; \alpha, c, k, n).$$

The main contrast is Δ_{23} ; the contrasts Δ_{25}, Δ_{27} play the role of negative controls.

We summarize each tower by mean absolute contrasts over the computed levels. Let $\mathcal{N}(\pi; \alpha, c, k)$ be the set of levels effectively computed for that cell, and let

$$\mathcal{N}_{\geq 2}(\pi; \alpha, c, k) := \{n \in \mathcal{N}(\pi; \alpha, c, k) : n \geq 2\}.$$

We define the mean absolute contrasts (when $\mathcal{N}_{\geq 2} \neq \emptyset$):

$$\text{MeanAbs } \Delta_{ab}(\pi; \alpha, c, k) := \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_{\geq 2}(\pi; \alpha, c, k)|} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_{\geq 2}(\pi; \alpha, c, k)} |\Delta_{ab}(\pi; \alpha, c, k, n)|.$$

The control-prime dominance ratio then quantifies whether the main contrast dominates the control contrasts:

$$R_{\text{ctrl}}(\pi; \alpha, c, k) := \frac{\text{MeanAbs } \Delta_{23}(\pi; \alpha, c, k)}{\max(\text{MeanAbs } \Delta_{25}(\pi; \alpha, c, k), \text{MeanAbs } \Delta_{27}(\pi; \alpha, c, k))} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}.$$

Heuristically, $R_{\text{ctrl}} > 1$ means the 2–3 separation exceeds the separation against controls; empirically we report $R_{\text{ctrl}} \leq 1$ in the explored grid. Section 7 explains why this

is consistent with the coherence findings: β_0 captures connectivity, while Coh_π is the diagnostic specifically designed to detect arithmetic structure.

The Phase I outcomes also support two binary predicates: $\text{RZ23}(\pi; \Xi)$ for *robust collapse* of the 2–3 contrast across the explored grid, and $\text{Ex23}(\pi; \Xi)$ for *existence* of a nonzero 2–3 contrast in the same grid. Their formal definitions and the per-piece outcomes are deferred to the Online Supplement (Appendix D); the main text relies only on the integrated quantities Δ_{ab} and R_{ctrl} above.

6 Results

The central results are the inverse-system coherence diagnostic Coh_π (§6.1), the matched-branching check at $r = p = 3$ (§6.2), and the permutation null model (§6.3); the graph-connectivity results (§6.4) provide a complementary view. Phase I (β_0, Δ_{23}) is reported for all six movements of BWV 1007 (Table 7); Coh_π and the null model use the Prelude and Sarabande as benchmark subset. The file `cs1.1pre` is byte-identical with the file labelled `prelude`; we use `cs1.1pre` throughout. Extended tables and figures are in the Online Supplement (Appendix D).

6.1 Profinite coherence with enforced π

The hierarchical construction of Section 4.6 yields dictionaries (S_n) with explicit morphisms $\pi_{n+1,n}$ and the score $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ defined in Eq. (3), with denominator p^{n+1} . Table 3 summarizes mean $\text{Coh}_\pi(2)$, mean $\text{Coh}_\pi(3)$, and mean ΔCoh_π over levels n for the benchmark subset (Prelude, Sarabande, toy binary, toy ternary) and both axes, with the hyperparameters of Table 2.

Table 3 Hierarchical coherence summary (enforced $\pi_{n+1,n}$). Mean $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ over available levels n and mean $\Delta\text{Coh}_\pi(n) = \text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) - \text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$.

Piece	Axis	mean $\text{Coh}_\pi(2)$	mean $\text{Coh}_\pi(3)$	mean ΔCoh_π
cs1.1pre	beats	0.5000	0.9712	-0.4712
cs1.1pre	seconds	0.5000	0.8786	-0.3786
cs1.4sar	beats	0.4922	0.9990	-0.5068
cs1.4sar	seconds	0.5000	0.9619	-0.4619
toy_binary	beats	0.5000	0.8128	-0.3128
toy_binary	seconds	0.5000	0.6728	-0.1728
toy_ternary	beats	0.5000	0.8220	-0.3220
toy_ternary	seconds	0.5000	0.7058	-0.2058

Parameters: $K=16$, $r=2$, $M=800$, $\text{step}=2$, $\text{seed}=42$. Data: `coherence_pi_p2.csv`, `coherence_pi_p3.csv` per piece/axis.

Conditions (SC) and (AI) were verified computationally on the audited full-sibling parent classes in the implemented pipeline for all benchmark runs (BWV1007 suite, parameters $K = 16$, $r = 2$, seed 42): for each $n = 1, \dots, 5$ and both time axes, the per-parent audit (`audit_p2.csv`) shows $\text{match}(n) = \text{valid}_b(n)$, equivalently $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(2, n) = 1$, so every valid level- $(n + 1)$ residue is coherent. The headline raw

score then satisfies $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = \text{Cov}(2, n + 1)/2$, equal to $1/2$ in the dense regime and slightly below $1/2$ where coverage drops by a single residue. This establishes the hypotheses of Lemma 1 on full-sibling parents and the sparse-coverage correction of Corollary 2 otherwise.

The extended suites BWV 1008 and BWV 1009 reproduce the same pattern: on the beats axis, $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = 0.500$ across all dense levels in every movement, while $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$ stays comfortably above the floor $1/3$ (movement-level means in $[0.70, 0.98]$). The seconds axis weakens the $p = 3$ signal, consistent with the axis sensitivity already documented for BWV 1007. Full per-level data and the BWV 1008–1009 movement table are in the reproducibility bundle (Online Supplement, Appendix D).

For external Bach pieces (BWV1049, BWV1050, BWV1079, BWV988), Phase I was run with control primes $p \in \{2, 3, 5, 7\}$ (cap = 300). Hierarchical Coh_π for the external Bach corpus is in Table 4; the Mozart extension (K.331, K.545) is in preparation and not included in this report.

Table 4: External corpus: hierarchical Coh_π (and Coh_{grid}) at $n \geq 2$. Bach: BWV1079 (Crab Canon), BWV1049–1050 (Brandenburg Concertos 4–5, all movements), BWV988 (Goldberg Aria). Mozart (K.331, K.545): in preparation.

Piece	Axis	p	n	Coh_{pi}	Coh_{grid}
bwv1049_mov1	beats	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1049_mov1	beats	2	3	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1049_mov1	beats	2	4	0.4375	0.4375
bwv1049_mov1	beats	2	5	0.3750	0.3750
bwv1049_mov1	beats	3	2	1.0000	1.0000
bwv1049_mov1	beats	3	3	0.7654	0.7654
bwv1049_mov1	beats	3	4	0.4897	0.5185
bwv1049_mov1	beats	5	2	0.6480	0.6720
bwv1049_mov1	beats	7	2	0.6472	0.6968
bwv1049_mov2	beats	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1049_mov2	beats	2	3	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1049_mov2	beats	2	4	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1049_mov2	beats	2	5	0.4062	0.4062
bwv1049_mov2	beats	3	2	0.8148	0.8148
bwv1049_mov2	beats	3	3	0.4198	0.4321
bwv1049_mov2	beats	3	4	0.3539	0.3827
bwv1049_mov2	beats	5	2	0.5200	0.5280
bwv1049_mov2	beats	7	2	0.6297	0.6939
bwv1049_mov3	beats	2	2	0.2500	0.2500
bwv1049_mov3	beats	2	3	0.3125	0.3125
bwv1049_mov3	beats	2	4	0.4375	0.4375
bwv1049_mov3	beats	2	5	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1049_mov3	beats	3	2	0.7407	0.7778
bwv1049_mov3	beats	3	3	0.3951	0.3951
bwv1049_mov3	beats	3	4	0.3416	0.3745
bwv1049_mov3	beats	5	2	0.6000	0.6880
bwv1049_mov3	beats	7	2	0.4315	0.4286
bwv1050_mov1	beats	2	2	0.3750	0.3750
bwv1050_mov1	beats	2	3	0.3125	0.3125
bwv1050_mov1	beats	2	4	0.2500	0.2500
bwv1050_mov1	beats	2	5	0.4688	0.4688
bwv1050_mov1	beats	3	2	0.8889	0.8889
bwv1050_mov1	beats	3	3	0.5309	0.6173
bwv1050_mov1	beats	3	4	0.5556	0.6008
bwv1050_mov1	beats	5	2	0.5440	0.5920
bwv1050_mov1	beats	7	2	0.4606	0.5160
bwv1050_mov2	beats	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1050_mov2	beats	2	3	0.2500	0.2500
bwv1050_mov2	beats	2	4	0.3438	0.3438
bwv1050_mov2	beats	2	5	0.2188	0.2188

Piece	Axis	p	n	Coh_pi	Coh_grid
bwv1050_mov2	beats	3	2	0.7037	0.7037
bwv1050_mov2	beats	3	3	0.4321	0.4321
bwv1050_mov2	beats	3	4	0.4115	0.4115
bwv1050_mov2	beats	5	2	0.7200	0.7600
bwv1050_mov2	beats	7	2	0.4140	0.4636
bwv1050_mov3	beats	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1050_mov3	beats	2	3	0.4375	0.4375
bwv1050_mov3	beats	2	4	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1050_mov3	beats	2	5	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1050_mov3	beats	3	2	0.9630	0.9630
bwv1050_mov3	beats	3	3	0.8148	0.8025
bwv1050_mov3	beats	3	4	0.4856	0.5267
bwv1050_mov3	beats	5	2	0.5440	0.6480
bwv1050_mov3	beats	7	2	0.3673	0.4373
bwv1079_crab	beats	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1079_crab	beats	2	3	0.5000	0.5000
bwv1079_crab	beats	2	4	0.4688	0.5000
bwv1079_crab	beats	2	5	0.3594	0.3594
bwv1079_crab	beats	3	2	0.5556	0.7037
bwv1079_crab	beats	3	3	0.5679	0.5802

Mozart (K.331, K.545): pipeline in preparation; data to appear in a forthcoming companion note.

The external table is the clearest evidence that Coh_π should be read as a diagnostic for the operating conditions of the tower rather than as a universal floor law. Several polyphonic movements fall below the matched binary floor at some levels (for instance BWV1049 mov. 3 and BWV1050 movs. 1–2), which means that at least one of the hypotheses behind Lemma 1 fails in those configurations. The informative signal is therefore not the identity $\text{Coh}_\pi = 1/p$ itself, but the location and direction of departures from it across texture, level, and prime.

Figures 2 and 3 show $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ and $\Delta\text{Coh}_\pi(n)$ vs. n for the Prelude (beats axis); Figures 4 and 5 for the Sarabande (beats axis).

Fig. 2 $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ vs level n , hierarchical construction, Prelude, beats.

6.2 Matched-branching check: $r = p = 3$

Lemma 1 predicts that the coherence falls to the null floor $1/p$ when the branching factor r matches the prime p , provided the sibling separation condition (SC) and the

Fig. 3 $\Delta\text{Coh}_\pi(n)$ vs n , Prelude, beats.

Fig. 4 $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ vs n , Sarabande, beats.

ancestor inclusion condition (AI) hold. To test this, we re-ran the hierarchical pipeline with $r = 3$ (flag `--Kchild 3`) for four pieces (Prelude, Sarabande, toy binary, toy ternary) at both $p = 2$ and $p = 3$.

Table 5 reports the results alongside the standard $r = 2$ values. The key comparison is $p = 3, r = 3$: the Prelude (binary meter) drops from $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, 3) = 0.90$ at $r = 2$ to $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, 3) = 0.36$ at $r = 3$, approaching the predicted floor $1/3 \approx 0.333$. The Sarabande (ternary emphasis), by contrast, stays at $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, 3) = 0.90$ at $r = 3$ (down only marginally from $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, 3) = 1.00$ at $r = 2$), far above $1/3$. This is consistent with ternary temporal structure breaking (SC), but the experiment does not by itself isolate meter from density, phrasing, length, or articulation. At $p = 2$ with $r = 3$, the coherence remains at $1/2$ across all pieces, consistent with $r \neq p$ leaving the $p = 2$ tower unaffected.

These data verify the matched-branching prediction computationally on the four pieces tested: switching to $r = p = 3$ collapses $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, \cdot)$ toward $1/3$ on the Prelude but leaves it elevated on the Sarabande. On this sample the test behaves asymmetrically, but the conclusion is deliberately local. Extending the $r = 3$ check to all six BWV1007 movements and to the polyphonic corpus is a direct next experiment; until then, the

Fig. 5 $\Delta\text{Coh}_\pi(n)$ vs n , Sarabande, beats.

Sarabande/Prelude contrast should be read as a controlled illustration rather than as a corpus-level law.

6.3 Statistical assessment: permutation null model

The elevation of $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$ above $1/2$ could, in principle, arise from the architecture of the hierarchical quantizer rather than from temporal structure in the signal. To control for this, we applied the permutation null model of Section 5.3 ($B = 100$ replicates, $p = 3$, beats axis) to the four benchmark pieces.

Table 6 reports the observed $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$, the null distribution (median, 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles), and the one-sided p -value at each level. For the Sarabande, the p -values at levels $n = 2, 3, 4$ are 0.030, < 0.01 , and 0.030, respectively: the observed coherence exceeds 97% or more of the null replicates. The Prelude shows p -values above 0.30 at all levels; the observed $\text{Coh}_\pi(3)$ values lie within the null envelope, as expected for a binary signal probed by the ternary tower. The toys (binary and ternary) likewise show p -values ≥ 0.56 , as expected for short synthetic signals where permutation preserves pattern structure to within the null envelope.

The Sarabande finding indicates that the elevation $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n) > 1/2$ depends on temporal structure in this signal: destroying temporal order via row permutation reduces the coherence to a distribution centered near 0.5–0.6, whereas the observed values (1.00, 1.00, 0.95) sit at or above the upper tail.

6.4 Complementary graph-connectivity results

These results complement, rather than replace, the inverse-system coherence findings of Section 6.1: the profinite-map coherence $\text{Coh_exact}(p, n)$ (Section 4.5), the tower graph invariants β_0 and giant-component fraction, the separation landscape $\Delta(n, k)$, the k -persistence surrogate, and the control-prime analysis with $p \in \{5, 7\}$ provide an independent, single-level perspective on the same data. Phase I connectivity is reported for all six movements of BWV 1007 in Table 7; full per-level tables and figures are in the Online Supplement (Appendix D).

Table 5 Check of Lemma 1 with $r = 3$: $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ for $r = 2$ (default) vs $r = 3$. Predicted floor when $r = p/1/p$.

Piece	p	n	$\text{Coh}_\pi (r=2)$	$\text{Coh}_\pi (r=3)$
Prelude	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
Prelude	2	3	0.5000	0.5000
Prelude	2	4	0.5000	0.5000
Prelude	2	5	0.5000	0.5000
Prelude	3	2	1.0000	1.0000
Prelude	3	3	0.9012	0.3580
Prelude	3	4	0.9835	0.5267
Sarabande	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
Sarabande	2	3	0.5000	0.5000
Sarabande	2	4	0.4688	0.4688
Sarabande	2	5	0.4375	0.4688
Sarabande	3	2	1.0000	1.0000
Sarabande	3	3	1.0000	0.9012
Sarabande	3	4	0.9959	0.8436
Toy binary	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
Toy binary	2	3	0.5000	0.5000
Toy binary	2	4	0.5000	0.5000
Toy binary	2	5	0.4688	0.4688
Toy binary	3	2	1.0000	0.5926
Toy binary	3	3	0.9630	0.2593
Toy binary	3	4	0.2881	0.0946
Toy ternary	2	2	0.5000	0.5000
Toy ternary	2	3	0.5000	0.5000
Toy ternary	2	4	0.5000	0.5000
Toy ternary	2	5	0.5000	0.4219
Toy ternary	3	2	1.0000	0.4074
Toy ternary	3	3	1.0000	0.2716
Toy ternary	3	4	0.2881	0.0000

The complementary connectivity results are summarized by the separation landscape. The contrast $\Delta(n, k)$ of equation (1), viewed jointly over level n and neighborhood size k , is shown in Figure 6 (beats axis, Prelude). Positive values indicate more components at $p = 2$; negative favor $p = 3$. The beats axis exhibits nonzero Δ across more (n, k) cells than the seconds axis; Table 7 shows that this pattern holds across the full suite.

The control-dominance ratio

$$R_{\text{ctrl}} = \frac{\text{MeanAbs } \Delta_{23}}{\max(\text{MeanAbs } \Delta_{25}, \text{MeanAbs } \Delta_{27})} \quad (6)$$

remains at or below 1 throughout the explored grid: at the resolution of β_0 , the $p = 2$ vs. $p = 3$ separation lies within the control baseline. This level-specific behavior of β_0 motivates the profinite coherence layer, which provides level-uniform discrimination. On the synthetic side, Table 3 includes `toy_binary` and `toy_ternary`: mean $\text{Coh}_\pi(3)$

Table 6 Permutation null model for $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$ ($r = 2$, beats axis, $B = 100$).
 p -value: fraction of null replicates \geq observed.

Piece	n	Observed	Null med.	Null 2.5%	Null 97.5%	p -value
Prelude	1	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Prelude	2	1.0000	1.0000	0.3861	1.0000	0.5446
Prelude	3	0.8519	0.6296	0.3827	1.0000	0.3267
Prelude	4	0.6296	0.7407	0.5508	0.9387	0.8713
Sarabande	1	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Sarabande	2	1.0000	0.5370	0.1815	0.9630	0.0297
Sarabande	3	1.0000	0.5370	0.2892	0.8466	<0.01
Sarabande	4	0.9465	0.6296	0.2970	0.8954	0.0297
Toy binary	1	0.5556	0.7778	0.4444	1.0000	0.9307
Toy binary	2	0.5926	0.5926	0.2963	0.8343	0.5644
Toy binary	3	0.3086	0.4938	0.3333	0.6667	0.9901
Toy binary	4	0.1317	0.2634	0.2324	0.2820	1.0000
Toy ternary	1	0.2222	1.0000	0.2222	1.0000	1.0000
Toy ternary	2	0.4074	0.7407	0.4074	1.0000	0.9802
Toy ternary	3	0.2716	0.5185	0.2898	0.7907	0.9802
Toy ternary	4	0.0000	0.2510	0.2118	0.2779	1.0000

Table 7 BWV 1007 full suite: Phase I connectivity. Per movement and axis, $n_{nz}(\Delta_{23}) = \text{count of } (n, k) \text{ with } \Delta_{23} \neq 0$ over $n \geq 2, k \in \{8, 10, 12\}$; $|\overline{\Delta_{23}}| = \text{mean over those cells. Config A, cap 300.}$

Movement	Axis	$n_{nz}(\Delta_{23})$	$ \overline{\Delta_{23}} $
Prelude	seconds	5	0.92
Prelude	beats	11	1.42
Allemande	seconds	3	0.42
Allemande	beats	8	1.17
Courante	seconds	3	2.25
Courante	beats	6	1.00
Sarabande	seconds	0	0.00
Sarabande	beats	9	1.33
Menuets	seconds	0	0.00
Menuets	beats	9	1.58
Gigue	seconds	9	4.00
Gigue	beats	7	0.67

exceeds mean $\text{Coh}_\pi(2)$ for all pieces, and the control primes $p = 5, 7$ are computed for external pieces in the Online Supplement (Table D.1).

7 Discussion

The three layers of this work form a single framework: the arithmetic tower $\{D_{p,n}\}$, the architectural floor $\text{Coh}_\pi = 1/p$ in the matched-branching regime $r = p$ (Lemma 1 and Corollary 2), and the empirical tests that determine when the hypotheses behind that floor hold. The tower fixes the scale ladder by algebraic canonicity; the

Fig. 6 Separation landscape $\Delta(n, k)$: beats axis, config A, piece `cs1.1pre`. Rows = level n , columns = k .

coherence diagnostic Coh_π measures compatibility with that ladder; and the experiments locate where this compatibility behaves architecturally and where it becomes signal-dependent.

Within this framework, the robust part of the empirical signal is a structured dependence on level and protocol rather than a single global binary–ternary separation. The separation landscape (Figure 6) shows that $\Delta(n, k)$ varies with both n and k : the beats axis exhibits nonzero Δ across more (n, k) cells than the seconds axis. Extended k -persistence and seconds-axis figures are in the Online Supplement (Appendix D).

This is why the inverse-system layer has a different status from the single-level graph summaries. The hierarchical construction of Section 4.6 imposes structural compatibility via explicit morphisms $\pi_{n+1, n} : S_{n+1} \rightarrow S_n$, so that compatibility is enforced rather than measured post hoc. The resulting score $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n)$ (Eq. 3) measures how closely the induced finite-level maps $f_{p, n}$ approximate, in the inverse-system sense, an element of the conjectural limit $\text{Cont}(\mathbb{Z}_p, S)$ (cf. Problem 3). The underlying continuous target and the quantizer q_n depend on the MIR representation and hyperparameters; enforcing $\pi_{n+1, n}$ removes the main conceptual ambiguity of level-wise learning.

The main empirical finding should therefore be read as a departure from the architectural floor correlated with texture on the tested corpus, rather than as a universal law. Given Lemma 1 and Corollary 2, the comparison $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n)$ vs. $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$ is asymmetric in status. For $p = 2$ with $r = p = 2$, the value $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = 1/2$ is forced under (SC)+(AI); the binary tower is therefore at the architectural floor whenever those hypotheses hold, and the computational verification $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = 0.500$ on every benchmark run is evidence that they hold in the monophonic BWV1007 configuration. The diagnostic at this configuration reads as architectural rather than signal-driven.

The external Bach table changes the interpretation. Polyphonic movements sometimes fall below the binary floor and sometimes depart from it at high levels, so the score is most useful as a detector of where the architectural-floor hypotheses cease to describe the data. For $p = 3$ with $r = 2 \neq p = 3$, the underbranched regime (Remark 3)

leaves the score free to reflect signal structure; we observe $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n) \in [0.67, 0.999]$ on the benchmark and $[0.34, 0.999]$ on the full corpus. We read these values as evidence that the finite-level maps retain temporal information beyond the matched binary configuration, rather than as a universal ternary law.

Coh_π is therefore a finite-level compatibility diagnostic for the enforced hierarchy, not a causal test isolating a single failed condition. A direct audit of the local numerator, separating the effective π -based assignment from the truncation-based assignment, shows on the audited corpus that ancestor inclusion remains largely satisfied while sibling separation under the effective π -based assignment collapses more frequently; departures from the floor are accordingly not explained by a one-condition failure mechanism.

The two normalizations of Eqs. (3)–(4) are complementary. The raw score Coh_π , with denominator p^{n+1} , is bounded by $\text{Cov}(p, n+1)$ and is the natural quantity for cross-prime comparisons, since both primes share the same architectural denominator. The conditional score $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}$ removes the coverage factor and isolates compatibility on the observed residues. In the $p=2$, step-2 runs of this paper only half of the level- $(n+1)$ residues are valid, so $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) \leq 1/2$ structurally, while $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(2, n) = 1$ throughout the BWV1007 Prelude on the beats axis. The two scores jointly identify the architectural floor (raw) and its inner saturation (valid), neither of which is a direct claim about musical content.

The control-prime results clarify the narrower role of the graph-connectivity layer. The control-prime dominance ratio $R_{\text{ctrl}} \leq 1$ throughout the explored grid (Section 6.4) means that the $p=2$ vs. $p=3$ separation in β_0 remains at or below the separation against the pre-registered controls $p \in \{5, 7\}$. This is a genuine *level-specific* property of the tower graph invariants, with the discriminating signal concentrated in the intermediate range of n : for the BWV1007 Prelude (beats axis, config A), $\beta_0(p=2) - \beta_0(p=3) = 5$ at $n=2$ and -2 at $n=5$, while for the Crab Canon (BWV1079) all four primes yield distinct β_0 values simultaneously at $n=1$. At large n , the discriminating signal merges with a connectivity ceiling: for window lengths $N = p^n$ large relative to the piece duration, β_0 saturates at 1 for all p as the graph becomes fully connected, and cross-prime contrast reflects corpus density rather than p .

The inverse-system coherence layer is complementary, addressing whether the hierarchical maps are compatible with the reduction structure of $\{\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}\}_n$ and providing a *level-uniform* arithmetic discriminant across the full range of n . A formal characterisation of when the arithmetic filtration outperforms a geometric one is left as Open Problem 2.

The profinite language is read with the finite-level qualification of Section 4: an organizing principle, not a realized structure. The K -means quantizer used here produces unstructured finite sets S_n , and neither group structure nor group-compatibility of $\pi_{n+1, n}$ is established by the current construction. A genuine profinite-limit interpretation, in which $\varprojlim S_n$ would be a profinite abelian group and the induced maps $f_{p, n}$ would admit Mahler expansions (Gouvêa, 2020; Mahler, 1958, Ch. 4) on $\text{Cont}(\mathbb{Z}_p, \varprojlim S_n)$, would require a group-equivariant replacement of the quantizer and

independent evidence that the lifted coefficients carry musicological content. This paper neither claims that interpretation nor relies on it; both are deferred to Problem 3.

Limitations.

- **Algebraic canonicity is internal; phenomenological adequacy is empirical.** The canonicity of the ladder p^n lives inside the ring structure of \mathbb{Z} (Section 4.2); whether it captures a given musical phenomenon better than alternative scalings is an experimental question that depends on the corpus, protocol, and observable.
- **Corpus and protocol.** Conclusions are stated for the corpus tested (BWV 1007 primary; BWV 1008–1009 extended; external Bach BWV 1049, 1050, 1079, 988; Mozart K.331, K.545 in preparation) and for the documented protocol (Section 5); extension to broader k ranges, larger caps, alternative binnings, and the $r = 3$ matched-branching check beyond the Prelude, Sarabande, and the two toy signals is available within the same pipeline.
- **Scope of (SC) and (AI).** Lemma 1 characterises the architectural floor under (SC) and (AI); extending these conditions to arbitrary signals or quantizer initialisations is Problem 1.
- **Layer-specific reach.** Graph-connectivity invariants discriminate at intermediate n and saturate at large n ($R_{\text{ctrl}} \leq 1$ across the explored grid); the inverse-system coherence layer provides level-uniform discrimination. Each layer addresses what the other does not.

8 Conclusion

We introduced the arithmetically indexed tower $\{D_{p,n}\}_n$ with $N = p^n$, the inverse-system coherence diagnostic $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = M_\pi(p, n)/p^{n+1}$ together with its conditional companion $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n) = M_\pi(p, n)/|V_{p,n+1}|$, and a reproducible pipeline. The architectural floor is Lemma 1 (and its Corollary 2): in the dense regime, $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = \text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(p, n) = 1/p$ when $r = p$, under the verifiable conditions (SC) and (AI); in the sparse regime, $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = P_n^{\text{full}}/p^{n+1}$, with P_n^{full} the number of parent classes with all p siblings valid. The empirical content is the verification of these conditions on the BWV1007 benchmark ($\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = 1/2$ across dense levels and $\text{Coh}_\pi^{\text{valid}}(2, n) = 1$ on the Prelude), departures from the floor correlated with texture on the external Bach corpus, the asymmetric behavior of $\text{Coh}_\pi(3, n)$ above the architectural floor $1/3$ in the underbranched regime, and the targeted $r = p = 3$ check on four pieces.

The remaining questions are best stated as three open problems, separating the null-floor mechanism, the arithmetic filtration, and the possible profinite lift.

Open Problem 1 (Proving conditions (SC) and (AI) for the null floor). *Lemma 1 shows that $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) = 1/p$ when $r = p$ in the dense regime, under the sibling separation condition (SC) and the ancestor inclusion condition (AI); Corollary 2 extends this to the sparse-coverage regime in terms of P_n^{full} . The empirical data (Table 3) report $\text{Coh}_\pi(2, n) = 1/2$ across all dense levels for every benchmark piece, consistent with (SC)+(AI) holding on full-sibling parents throughout. The open problem is to establish these conditions from first principles:*

- (i) Prove or disprove that for a hierarchical K -means quantizer with $r = p$ children per node and generic initialization, (SC) holds for all $n \geq 1$ and all (non-degenerate) time series \mathcal{X} . Here “generic” means independently of the signal structure.
- (ii) Prove or disprove that (AI) follows from (SC) under the assumption that $W_{p,n}(a)$ is the componentwise median of the p truncated sibling windows $\{\text{trunc}(W_{p,n+1}(b_i))\}$.
- (iii) Characterize whether the failure of (SC) when $r < p$ is equivalent to the condition

$$\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) > 1/r,$$

and whether the degree of violation of (SC) determines the excess $\text{Coh}_\pi - 1/r$.

- (iv) Extend the $r = p = 3$ check beyond the four pieces of Section 6.2. The current data show collapse toward $1/3$ for the Prelude and persistent elevation for the Sarabande, but a corpus-level claim requires all BWV1007 movements and the polyphonic corpus.

Open Problem 2 (Arithmetic versus geometric filtration). Let $\beta_0^{\text{arith}}(p, n)$ denote the number of connected components of the k NN graph at arithmetic level n , and $\beta_0^{\text{geom}}(\varepsilon)$ the analogous quantity for a Vietoris–Rips filtration at scale ε . Under what conditions on the time series \mathcal{X} and on the correspondence $\varepsilon = \varepsilon(p, n)$ does the arithmetic filtration detect structural features that the geometric filtration misses? Given that $d(W, W')^2 = \|f_W - f_{W'}\|_{L^2(\mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z}, \mu_n)}^2$, characterize whether the $L^2(\mathbb{Z}_p, \mu_p)$ norm provides a structural advantage over a time-domain ε -filtration for signals with p -adic hierarchical structure.

Open Problem 3 (Profinite lifting and group-equivariant quantizer). Let $(S_n, \pi_{n+1,n})$ be the enforced inverse system of Section 4.6 and let $f_{p,n} : \mathbb{Z}/p^n\mathbb{Z} \rightarrow S_n$ be the induced maps.

- (i) Give sufficient conditions on \mathcal{X} and the quantizer (q_n) under which $\text{Coh}_\pi(p, n) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.
- (ii) Characterize the MIDI-derived sequences for which a lifting to a continuous map exists:

$$f \in \text{Cont}(\mathbb{Z}_p, \varprojlim S_n).$$

(cf. Problem 3).

- (iii) If the S_n are equipped with abelian group structure and the $\pi_{n+1,n}$ are surjective group homomorphisms, the limit $\varprojlim S_n$ is a profinite abelian group and the liftable sequences form a closed subspace of $C(\mathbb{Z}_p, \mathbb{R})$ admitting a Mahler expansion (Gouvêa, 2020, Ch. 4). Determine whether a group-equivariant quantizer achieves this, and whether the Mahler coefficients c_k of the lifted map carry musicological content (mean c_0 , linear trend c_1 , rhythmic micro-variation c_k for $k \geq 2$).

These open problems connect to a foundational treatment in terms of pro-objects and group-compatible quantizers, deferred to subsequent work. Immediate extensions include the full $r = 3$ replication, richer observables (flux, IOI, spectral gap), persistent homology in k , a group-equivariant quantizer (Problem 3), and more structured null models (e.g. Markov-chain preservation of local autocorrelation).

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Data availability. All MIDI files used are in the public domain or licensed under Creative Commons terms (see Section 5.1). Pipeline code, scripts, and reproducibility manifests, together with raw CSV outputs and aggregated summary tables, will be released in a public repository upon acceptance; an anonymised archive containing the full reproducibility bundle is available to editors and referees from the corresponding author upon request.

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